

Bromometric Determination of Enol Contents of Some β -Diketones

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(Received 7 December, 1971)

Enolisation of acetoacet-ortho-toluidide (AATH), 2,4-acetoacetylidide (AAXH), acetoacet-ortho-chloro anilide (CAAAH), acetoacet-ortho-anisidide (OAAAH) and α -benzoyl-meta-nitroacetanilide (NBAAH) have been studied in ethanol, methanol, dioxane and their water mixtures, by bromometric method and its dependance upon the time interval between the addition of bromine and quenching with phenol has been observed. The largest influence on the results was noted in polar solvents. On the assumption that bromination occurs instantaneously, discrete quench time results were extrapolated to zero time and enol contents at zero quench time have been calculated.

Determination of enol contents of β -diketones and β -ketoesters is of great importance in many physico-chemical investigations. Most commonly used technique is that of Meyer^{1,2} which is based upon the bromination of enol "double bond". Possibility of rapid keto-enol tautomerism during the analysis has not been considered. Several workers³⁻⁶ tried to limit this possibility. IR and ultraviolet techniques have also been employed^{5,6} to find the percentage of enol but the results were only semi-quantitative. The most important spectral technique at present is high resolution proton magnetic technique but it has limited application because many solvents are protonic themselves and interfere with the measurement of the tautomer resonance⁷⁻⁹. Mankad *et al.*¹⁰ have studied the enol contents in acetoacetylamides by Meyer's technique and recently we have reported¹¹ the determination of enol contents in acetoacetanilide and benzoylacetanilide by bromometric method.

The present studies were undertaken with a view to obtain total enol contents of acetoacet-ortho-toluidide (AATH), 2,4-acetoacetylidide (AAXH), acetoacet-ortho-chloro-anilide (CAAAH), acetoacet-ortho-anisidide (OAAAH) and benzoyl-meta-nitroacetanilide (NBAAH) in various solvent-water mixtures by using bromometric method¹². Attempt has also been made to determine the dependence of enol contents on the time interval between the addition of bromine and quenching with phenol in different solvents using the method suggested by Lochmuller¹³.

EXPERIMENTAL

Analytical or reagent grade aceto-acet-ortho-toluidide, 2,4-aceto-acetylidide, acetoacet-ortho-chloroanilide, and benzoyl-meta-nitro-acetanilide (Eastman Kodak, U.S.A.) and

acetoacet-ortho-anisidide (B.D.H., England) were used for experiments. All other chemicals used were of analytical or reagent grade quality.

Bromometric Measurement : An established^{1,2}, indirect bromometric procedure was used for all measurements. The technique involves the addition of excess of bromine to a 0.025*M* solution of AATH, AAXH, CAAAH and OAAAH and 0.01*M* solution of NBAAH respectively in different solvent-water mixtures. The excess of bromine was quenched at a fixed time interval with an excess of phenol. Bromoketone thus formed was treated with excess of KI solution and the liberated iodine was titrated with standard sodium thio-sulphate solution. In order to establish the effect of quench time on the observed results, three replicate determinations were made at an average of four different equispaced quench time intervals. The standard deviation of the mean ranged from 1–2% enol.

All measurements were made at $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$. The samples were equilibrated for 24–30 hrs at the experimental temperature before analysis. A blank consisting of the solvent alone was run at each quenching time.

Determination of enol % at zero quench time : The enol content at zero quench time was obtained by the extrapolation of the data obtained at various quench times to zero seconds. The extrapolation was also accomplished by polynomial least square regression analysis. This computation was accomplished by a programme POLRG from the Scientific Subroutine Package (SSP) of the IBM 1130 computing system. The data were fitted to a function of the general form

$$t = \text{time (sec.)}; \quad t_0 = \text{enol \% at } t = 0 \text{ sec.}$$

$$\text{Enol \%} = t_0 + a_1 t_1 + a_2 t_2^2 + a_3 t_3^3 + \dots + a_n t_n^n$$

Several polynomial orders were tried for each sample and the results reported are those derived from the fit which gave the smallest residual sum of squares. The indeterminacy in the value of t_0 averaged 2–3% relative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the bromometric determination are reported in Tables 1–5.

The strong dependence of the observed enol content on the time interval between the addition of bromine and the quenching agent, phenol, is quite evident (cf. Tables 1–5). From the results obtained in the case of methanol-water and ethanol-water mixtures, the enol content increased dramatically (over 100%) when the reaction was quenched at an interval of 30–40 sec. If the bromometric process is assumed to be instantaneous over the time period of the experiment then it is possible to extrapolate the data obtained at fixed quench time to zero second quench time. The results thus obtained are reported in Tables 1–5 under the heading ' t_0 '.

It is observed that the percentage of enol in AATH, AAXH, CAAAH, and OAAAH is less in the solvents of high polarity and *vice versa*. Since the keto form of a diketone is almost invariably more polar than the enol form, the [enol]/[keto] ratio for a given pair of tautomers at equilibrium in solution depends markedly on the polarity of the solvent and

TABLE 1

Observed enol % at various quench times for acetoacet-ortho-toluidide (AATH) at 30° in various solvent—water mixtures

Weight % Organic Solvent	Time (Sec.)					
	5	10	20	30	40	"t ₀ "
<i>Ethanol—Water</i>						
100.0	64.30	66.90	70.80	74.35	78.07	62.34
75.8	52.10	58.08	68.04	80.80	93.07	46.77
54.0	37.23	46.10	67.02	83.40	96.80	27.40
34.3	36.12	49.52	72.60	90.10	104.20	21.89
<i>Methanol—Water</i>						
100.0	61.00	63.08	65.43	68.01	70.58	60.05
76.2	54.30	57.03	61.72	66.49	71.09	51.84
54.6	40.62	48.44	64.06	75.78	85.92	31.46
34.7	31.65	39.06	51.56	63.28	73.81	24.61
<i>Dioxane—Water</i>						
100.0	81.14	82.62	85.59	88.57	91.54	79.65
80.5	47.26	50.23	55.82	61.41	67.00	44.43
60.8	37.20	43.20	57.30	67.30	74.40	30.36
40.8	32.70	37.90	47.24	55.82	60.26	28.30

TABLE 2

Observed enol % at various quench times for 2,4-acetoacetylidide (AAXH) at 30° in various solvent—water mixtures

Weight % Organic Solvent	Time (Sec.)					
	5	10	20	30	40	"t ₀ "
<i>Ethanol—Water</i>						
100.0	65.50	67.90	71.30	75.80	79.70	63.35
75.8	54.30	61.75	74.40	85.56	93.00	46.16
54.0	49.50	61.75	80.40	92.30	98.20	36.14
34.3	40.40	53.57	76.20	93.74	107.90	26.63
<i>Methanol—Water</i>						
100.0	61.30	63.42	66.10	68.07	72.05	60.05
76.2	58.80	68.45	84.82	96.00	102.70	47.71
54.6	55.06	70.30	89.65	104.20	111.60	38.54
34.7	49.80	65.10	91.14	105.60	111.60	31.02
<i>Dioxane—Water</i>						
100.0	82.20	82.60	83.30	84.07	84.82	81.85
80.5	56.20	60.60	67.70	74.80	81.90	51.62
60.8	36.80	44.60	57.70	70.70	78.10	30.41
40.8	29.40	33.50	40.90	48.70	53.60	26.30

TABLE 3

Observed enol % at various quench times for acetoacet-ortho-chloroanilide (CAAAH) at 30° in various solvent—water mixtures

Weight % Organic Solvent	Time (Sec.)					
	5	10	20	30	40	"t ₀ "
<i>Ethanol—Water</i>						
100.0	71.40	72.30	73.70	75.10	76.40	70.30
75.8	52.90	62.90	78.20	90.60	100.20	43.07
54.0	43.70	57.00	80.00	99.10	110.60	30.50
34.3	45.60	58.00	78.80	97.30	110.60	32.54
<i>Methanol—Water</i>						
100.0	68.80	69.70	71.00	72.40	74.50	68.20
76.2	55.80	65.00	80.20	89.90	96.80	45.79
54.6	56.70	66.80	84.40	96.80	106.00	45.47
34.7	43.70	56.70	79.80	96.80	110.60	29.51
<i>Dioxane—Water</i>						
100.0	83.70	84.40	85.60	87.10	88.50	83.11
80.5	59.10	62.70	67.30	70.00	74.20	53.85
60.8	46.10	49.80	56.20	59.90	63.60	41.00
40.8	35.00	39.60	52.10	61.30	69.20	29.58

TABLE 4

Observed enol % at various quench times for acetoacet-ortho-anisidide (OAAAH) at 30° in various solvent—water mixtures

Weight % Organic Solvent	Time (Sec.)					
	5	10	20	30	40	"t ₀ "
<i>Ethanol—Water</i>						
100.0	76.00	78.40	80.70	83.00	85.30	73.33
75.8	55.80	64.10	78.40	91.80	101.40	46.92
54.0	50.70	60.40	77.90	92.20	103.70	40.13
34.3	41.50	55.30	78.80	96.80	110.60	26.77
<i>Methanol—Water</i>						
100.0	71.00	71.90	73.80	75.60	77.50	70.06
76.2	55.80	62.20	73.80	84.40	92.20	49.66
54.6	48.40	59.50	76.90	89.90	101.40	35.15
34.7	46.10	60.80	82.10	96.80	106.00	29.08
<i>Dioxane—Water</i>						
100.0	83.90	84.80	87.10	89.40	91.70	83.05
80.5	64.50	69.20	76.20	81.10	88.10	58.13
60.8	46.60	53.90	66.80	78.40	87.60	38.89
40.8	35.00	40.10	50.30	59.90	66.90	30.42

TABLE 5

Observed enol % at various quench times for α -benzoyl-meta-nitro-acetanilide (NBAAH) at 30° in various solvent—water mixtures

Weight % Organic Solvent	Time (Sec.)					"t ₀ "
	5	10	20	30	40	
<i>Ethanol—Water</i>						
100.0	75.60	77.30	81.00	84.60	86.80	74.32
75.8	58.90	64.40	73.70	79.30	84.60	51.54
54.0	44.20	51.50	60.70	69.90	75.60	37.87
<i>Methanol—Water</i>						
100.0	69.90	71.80	73.60	75.40	77.30	67.96
76.2	55.20	58.90	64.40	69.90	73.60	51.64
54.6	46.00	49.70	55.20	60.70	64.40	42.44
<i>Dioxane—Water</i>						
100.0	82.40	84.30	86.20	88.10	90.00	80.30
80.5	64.70	69.00	76.60	84.30	88.10	61.54
60.8	48.80	56.50	69.00	77.60	81.40	40.41

this ratio tends to be greatest in the less polar solvents¹⁴. Also solvent with high dielectric constant destroys the internal hydrogen bonding (Structures I and II).

For AAATH	$\text{R}_1 = -\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{CH}_3)$ (ortho); $\text{R}_2 = -\text{CH}_3$
For AAXH,	$\text{R}_1 = -\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CH}_3)_2$; $\text{R}_2 = -\text{CH}_3$
For CAAAH,	$\text{R}_1 = -\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{Cl})$ (ortho); $\text{R}_2 = -\text{CH}_3$
For OAAAH,	$\text{R}_1 = -\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OCH}_3)$ (ortho); $\text{R}_2 = -\text{CH}_3$
For NBAAH,	$\text{R}_1 = -\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NO}_2)$ (meta); $\text{R}_2 = -\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

The importance of the internal hydrogen bonding is evident in all the cases studied by the decrease in enolisation in polar solvents because the carbonyl group is hydrogen bonded to water molecules¹⁵. This is in agreement with the view expressed by Murthy¹⁶ that in proton donating solvents, the major factor for the stabilisation of enol tautomer is hydrogen bonding because the enol form exists as the intramolecular hydrogen bonded species and it decreases the dipole-repulsion between the carbonyls. This accounts for the high percentage enol contents (cf. Tables 1–5) in solvents in which enol form can exist as the intermolecular hydrogen bonded species. The analysis of the results for AATH, AAXH, CAAH, and OAAAH in the cases of more polar solvents where the values are in excess of 100%

enol (Tables 1-4) at longer quenching time suggests a second enolisation process involving the bromoketone formed in the first instance

Thus the technique of extrapolation to zero second quench time can yield results which are generally valid.

Thanks of the authors are due to authorities BITS, Pilani for providing necessary facilities. The help rendered by Mr. A. V. John for computer programming is gratefully acknowledged.

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